

THE LENGTH - WEIGHT, LENGTH - LENGTH RELATIONSHIP AND CONDITION FACTOR OF
Oreochromis niloticus IN GBEDIKERE LAKE, BASSA, KOGI STATE.

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ABSTRACT

Length-weight, length-length relationships and condition factor of male, female and combined sex of *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa, Kogi State was studied. Seventy fish samples of total length ranging from 7.97cm to 19.50cm and weight between 20.8g and 309.4g collected between July and November 2008 were analyzed. Results showed that the male, females and combined sex had regression coefficient (b-value) of 2.76, 2.87, and 2.81 respectively. The males and females exhibited negative allometric growth. The length-length relationship had b-value of 1.18, -1.29, and -1.23 for males, females and combined sex respectively. Condition factor of the population varied from 1.53 to 5.62, females were in better condition than males. Condition factor between males and females was not significantly different ($P>0.05$). Gbedikere Lake is a good environment for growth, reproduction and survival of the *Oreochromis niloticus*.

KEYWORDS: Length-length relationship, condition factor, *Oreochromis niloticus*, Bassa, Kogi State.

INTRODUCTION

Fish found in tropical and sub-tropical water system experience frequency growth fluctuations due to factors such as food composition changes, environment changes, rate of spawning to mentioned but a few, length weight, and length-length relationship can be used to assess the influence of these factors in fish. Kulbicki *et al.*, (1993) and King (1966) reported that fish growth, mean weight of a given body length of fish estimation and the relative well being in fish can be known through this relationships length-weight, length-length relationships studies have been done in different water bodies and on different fishes. Notably among these are the report of King (1996) on some Nigerian fresh water fishes, Taiwo and Aransiola (2001) on *Chrysichthys* species in Asejire Lake, Fafioye and Oluajo (2005) on five fish species in Epe Lagoon, Nigeria and Laleye (2006) on *Oreochromis niloticus* in Oeume River in Benin.

Oreochromis niloticus is a fast growing and highly prolific species, though an indigenous Africa fish. It is also an inter-continental traveler (Bardach, *et.al.*, 1972). It has high tolerance to environmental conditions and its ability to accept compounded and natural feeds makes it economically cultivable and viable. It is characterized by the caudal fin with elongated body and a number of narrow bands on the back.

The study present information on the length-weight, length-length relationships and the condition factor of this valuable fish species is in order to aid the management of the lake.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

STUDY AREA

Lake Gbedikere is a natural lake located between Latitudes 3⁰24⁰ and Longitudes 5⁰14^E and is about 10km to the East of Oguma the Head quarter of Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State.

Water enters the Lake from tributaries that run from River Benue during rainy or flood season. When the season is over, the Lake separates out. The Lake is about 450m north of Gbedikere village. The water body covers about 400 – 450m and a depth of 10 – 14m deep, depending on the season.

The lake is used for fishing and other Domestic activities; consequently most of the settlers around the Lake are fishermen (Upper Benue River Basin Development Authority, 1985). The lake experience two seasonal periods; the rainy season starts in the month of May and last till October and is characterized by heavy down pour which

sometimes have an extensive flood action. The dry season is from late October to April and is characterized by cold, dusty -dry wind followed by intense heat.

The lake contains fish, other aquatic animals and some macrophytes such as wire grass (*Cyperus articulatus*) which are used for waving mats.

SAMPLES COLLECTION

Fish samples were identified and collected from the fishermen catches using gill nets, cast nets, hooks and lines and Malian traps between June and November 2008. Total length (cm) and weight (g) were taken using measuring board and top loading balance. Length-weight relationship was calculated using the formula: $W=aL^b$ which was transformed to logarithm of the form

$$\text{Log } W = \text{Log } a + b \text{ log } L$$

Using instat statistics package

Where W= body weight of the fish (g),
 L=total body length of fish (cm)
 a and b=values estimated by regression formula.

The condition factor (K) was calculated using the

$$K = \frac{100w}{L^3} \text{ (Pauly, 1984)}$$

Where K= condition factor, L=Total body length of fish (cm)
 W=body weight of fish (g).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A total of seventy species of *Oreochromis niloticus* were collected for the study. The length-weight frequency distribution of the fish species in Gbedikere Lake shown in Table 1. The standard length (cm) and their corresponding weights (g) are: Males 8.4cm – 19.5cm/23.5g – 309.4g, females 7.9cm – 18.6cm/20.8g – 208.5g, combined sex 7.9cm – 19.5cm/20.8g – 309.4g respectively.

Table 1: Length and weight frequency distribution of *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere Lake, Bassa, Kogi State.

Sex	Standard Length (cm)				Body Weight (g)		
	n	Min	Max	Mean ± S.D	Min	Max	Mean ± S.D
Males	35	8.40	19.50	14.01±3.11	23.5	309.4	109.97±2.81
Females	35	7.90	18.60	13.23±3.01	20.8	304.5	97.15±62.75
Combined sex	70	7.90	19.50	13.62±3.01	20.8	309.4	103.56±67.78

n=Number, Min=Minimum, Max=Maximum, SD = Standard Deviation.

The male length-weight relationship is expressed by the regression equation: $\text{Log } W = 0.066 + 2.758 \text{ Log } L$ (r = 0.9529) Fig 1.

The female length-weight relationship is expressed by the regression equation: $\text{Log } W = 0.511 + 2.8669 \text{ Log } L$ (r = 0.9609) Fig 2.

The combined sex's length-weight relationship is expressed by the regression equation: $\text{Log } W = 0.587 + 2.8078 \text{ Log } L$ ($r = 0.9574$) Fig 3.

Log length – log weight of males is expressed by the regression equation $\text{Log } W = 2.758 - 1.1801 \text{ Log } L$ ($r = 0.9529$) Fig 4.

Log length – log weight of females is expressed by the regression equation $\text{Log } W = 2.8669 - 1.2914 \text{ Log } L$ ($r = 0.9609$) Fig 5.

Log length – log weight of combined sexes is expressed by regression equation $\text{Log } W = 2.8078 - 1.2313 \text{ Log } L$ ($r = 0.9574$) Fig 6.

The length-length relationship also had a regression coefficient (b. values) of 1.1801, -1.2914 and -1.2313 for males, females and combined sexes respectively.

Table 2: Length-length relationship of *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere, Lake Bassa, Kogi State.

Sex	Total length (cm)						
	Min	Max	Mean \pm S.D	n	a	b	r
Males	11.2	24.3	17.75 \pm 3.04	35	2.758	1.1801	0.9529
Females	11.0	23.9	17.45 \pm 2.99	35	2.8669	-1.2914	0.9609
Combined sex	11.0	24.3	17.65 \pm 2.12	70	2.8078	-1.2313	0.9574

SD = Standard deviation, n=Number, a=Intercept, b=Slope, r=Coefficient of determination.

The condition factor (CF) ranged between 1.59 - 5.24, 2.14 – 5.62, and 5.62 for males, females and combined sexes (Table 3).

Table 3: Condition factor of *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere Lake Bassa, Kogi State.

Sex	Minimum	Maximum	Condition factor (k) (Mean \pm SD)
Males	1.59	5.24	3.58 \pm 0.68
Females	2.14	5.62	3.71 \pm 0.74
Combined sex	1.59	5.62	3.64 \pm 0.71

The b-values of 2.76, 2.87 and 2.81 indicate that males and females showed negative allometric growth, based on Begenal and Tesch (1978) criteria of 3. Similarly Pauly (1984) did report that a slope value greater than 3 denotes positive allometric growth that was not similar to the findings Anibeze (1995). This indicates that *Oreochromis niloticus* did not obeyed the cube law of growth (Le Cren, 1951) which is not commonly obeyed by most fishes. Etim (2000) and Fafioye and Oluajo (2005) respectively reported 2.951 and 3.042 b-value *Chrysichthys nigradigitatus* combined sex which are similar to the findings of the study. The value recorded during this study were similar with 1.53 to 2.55 reported by Ekanem (2006) for *Chrysichthys nigradigitatus* (Laceped) from Cross River and also higher than 0.79 \pm 0.15 which is less than 1.0 as reported by Fafioye and Oluajo (2006) from Epe Lagoon, this could be due to difference in the condition of the habitat such as Physico-Chemical parameters, plants and animal communities. Females have better condition factor than the males during the period of this study.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The composition of both sexes gave a better overview of length-weight relationship and condition factor of *Oreochromis niloticus*. The result of this study show negative allometric growth pattern, the b-values were generally in agreement with results for fishes of the same genus obtained from other geographical areas. Confirming that Gbedikere Lake in Bassa, Kogi State is a good environment for the growth, reproduction and survival of the species. The study provides basic information on the length-weight, length-length relationship and condition factor of *Oreochromis niloticus* that will be useful for fishery biologist and managers in Nigeria.

The in-depth studies on the length-weight, length-length relationship and condition factors; and other aspect of biology and biodiversity of *Oreochromis niloticus* towards sustainable management in Gbedikere Lake Bassa, Kogi State should be further elucidated.

Fig 3 Length- weight relationship of combined sexes of *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere Lake Bassa, Kogi State.

Fig 4 Log-length, Log-weight of male *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere Lake Bassa, Kogi State.

Fig 5 Log-length, Log-weight of male *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere Lake Bassa, Kogi State.

Fig 6 Log-length, Log-weight of combined sexes of *Oreochromis niloticus* in Gbedikere Lake Bassa, Kogi State.

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